

THE PRINCIPLES OF REALISM IN PROSE OF ZULFIYA KUROLBOY'S DAUGHTER

Eshmurzayeva is the daughter of Barno Osman

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

3rd year student of the Faculty of Uzbek Language and Literature

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Annotation: Zulfiya Kuroloy's stories and novels stand out among the works created in Uzbek literature due to their interestingness, impressiveness, realistic portrayal of human characters, and bold handling of complex life problems. The fact that the works of Z. Kuroloy's daughter have risen to the level of a serious phenomenon in literature determines the relevance of this article.

Key words: literature, Zulfiya, prose, realism, ideology.

For a long time, literary studies has adapted to examine the work of art mainly from the social point of view, but now, leaving the existing scientific patterns, it tries to approach it as a spiritual-emotional magical phenomenon based on aesthetic requirements.

In the current period of social renewal, great changes and development are taking place in the human personality, as a result of which the knowledge of the spiritual and spiritual world of students is becoming complex, and spiritual awakening and ideological renewal are felt in their minds. This process requires looking for ways to increase the impact of presenting examples of fiction to students. Although a wide range of scientific studies have been published in Uzbek literary studies on the analysis of works of art, until now there are still few cases of examining and presenting the work to the reader in terms of topical relevance and social significance. In the study of a work of art, the artistic text itself is the first place, and the age, party affiliation, gender, and experience of any creator are completely unimportant. Now the tasks before literary studies have changed: to study the work based on the text and to conclude in accordance with the nature of the text.

Zulfiya Kuroloy's stories and novels stand out among the works created in Uzbek literature for their interestingness, impressiveness, convincing embodiment of the reality of life and human characters, and for boldly raising the complex problems of life. In the works of the author, the characters, events, and endings that the reader is used to do not meet. These works have become an artistic phenomenon that cannot be ignored in Uzbek literature, and have gained their readers. Researching its specific features, determining its internal mechanism, the factors that ensure its artistry will allow a full understanding of current literature. Due to this necessity, this topic was tackled.

The purpose of the study. Based on the research and analysis of the works of Zulfiya Kuroloy's daughter, it is necessary to determine the specific aspects of the Uzbek literature of the independence period and the unique features of the creative prose works.

Research tasks:

- to determine the theoretical principles of the story and the direction of the image, the stages of development;
- monitoring and analyzing the news about the expression of national and universal values in literary stories;

- To determine the factors that ensure the originality of Zulfiya Kuroloy's work.

Research source. "Captive of Armenia" written by Zulfiya Kuroloy

The novels "Whirlpool of Troubles", "Ayol", "Hilola", "Oh, Life!", "Tafkkur", "Ikki Manzil", "Shadow" and similar stories were examined as a source of research.

The level of study of the problem. Although the talented writer Zulfiya Kuroloy enriches the treasure of our spirituality with a series of works that have raised the level of a serious phenomenon in literature, until today there are no studies in literary studies that analyze her work in detail. Until now, articles by literary scholars such as Umarali Normatov, Kazoqboy Yoldashev, Nusratilla Jumakhoja, Khurshid Dostmuhammad have been published on the author's works. Nilufar Heydarova compared the novel "Arman Asirasi" with the novel "Makon Istab" written by Jenny Erpenbek, Israilova In the works of Caodat Adiba, for example, there are graduate theses that examined the place of evolutions in the spirituality of the nation in the current narrative. In particular, Nilufar Haydarova believes that there is a connection between the main character of the novel "Makon istab" by the German writer Jenny Erpenbeck and Hulkar Armon, the hero of the novel "Armon Asira" by Zulfiya Kuroloy. Both novels are based on people's desire to reach their native place, to create their own place.

Summary

By gradually researching the creative maturity of Zulfiya Kuroloy's daughter from the time she entered the world of artistic creation until today, an attempt was made to show the reasons for the unique characteristics, achievements and shortcomings of the writer's prose works. In particular, many main features of the young writer's prose have been identified in the examples of the author's novels "Prisoner of Armon", "Whirlpool of Troubles" and several stories. Such characteristics include the author's deep artistic research of the female heart and character and the desire to express the truth about them, the plot is interesting and often unconventional, the problems of life are courageously covered, and noble social ideals are confirmed. These features were revealed through the analysis of Zulfiya Kuroloy's works "Ayol", "Hilola", "O, life!", "Tafakkur", "Ikki Manzil", "Shadow", "Whirlpool of Difficulties".

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